

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE THROUGH COMPUTER SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Computer is used in linguistic activity with multiple faces, summarized in three main pictures. Namely: general use, specific use, and specialized linguistic use. This paper tries to highlight the benefits and uses of computers in English Language teaching. Moreover, it aims to raise the consciousness of the benefits of computer technology in enlightening instruction for both teachers and learners.

Key Words: Computer, learning languages, learning theories, communication.

Since the seventh decade of the last century, computers have been used in language teaching and learning, which is called machine-assisted Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL): this involves the teaching of language elements and skills in different ways, as well as the creation, delivery and assessment of language tests [5].

There are many areas in which computers are used in purely linguistic or psychological research of languages. Maybe the most prominent of them: 1 – Use of speech synthesis in voice and psychological studies to identify the psychological characteristics that benefit human beings in recognizing linguistic voices, and researchers use the program to synthesize speech (speech synthesizer), as well as to present texts at different speeds in written recognition studies 2- Blog linguistics (corpus linguistics): this area is perhaps the most important field of linguistic research in recent decades in which the computer plays a vital role in the development of linguistic research at different levels and in different fields[3]. 3. Uses of database software (Data Base Management) (Access): Examples of using databases are some blogs. There are other sources for use in linguistic studies, however, such as error classification, using the database to identify errors according to their forms, grades, learner level, histories and abilities [6]. There is no doubt that, in addition to their benefits in the lexicon [7], there are many other uses of databases in linguistic research.

Some researchers are comparing this area with the previous field (linguistic research), owing to similarity and comparison. But differentiating between these two fields is desirable, the use of computers in linguistic research does not necessarily require the knowledge of linguistic computer programming, often referred to as some

writers in English as an ordinary working linguist (OWL), i.e., the ordinary linguist[5]. Computer linguistics combines linguistics with computer science (specialisation in computer programming). While a linguistics discipline, discipline, it is basically a programming operation focused on linguistic knowledge. That does not, however, prevent the presence of some experienced experienced computer programming linguists. There is no doubt that any successful computer-based linguistic project should combine the backlinks 465 Basmah Issa Ahmad AlSaleem between computer and language, either in one researcher or with the cooperation of linguists and computer specialists[8]. Computer linguistics experts are used to develop applications called Natural Language Processing Natural Language Processing (NLP), which includes: computer translation, text comprehension, automatic interpretation, character and sound recognition, automated sound creation, automated writing, spelling and grammar research, contextual perception concor dancer and other applications requires It is worth noting that software which understands the texts or dialogs with the machine needs artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, a specialty also in the field of computer science.

1. A-Comprehension: Some software is deactivated so that text appears on the screen, followed by type questions filling the void, right or wrong, or multiple choice, or asking about the meaning of a word or word type [1]. B-Text processing: such as allowing the rearrangement of a text sentence to be organized arbitrarily, or deleting the appearance of a document from it. Many words and expected terms would be picked from a list that could appear on the computer. CThe pace of reading, using special software, uses the timing factor to allow the learner to regulate the pace he needs.
2. Writing Skill Usage of word processing applications in writing, which allows the learner the ability to manage the text such as instant correction and spelling and pronunciation, use of various types of font and save pages, and the possibility to alter terms and adjust and arrange, and monitor the paragraphs and the space between the lines and the number of lines in the document. The preservation method helps the writer to re-browse and edit the written text[6]. And all this increases the student's success in speech and building, and makes spelling and writing more precise. There are several programs that support students , particularly in the simple stages of writing the hottest in the various ways, where you sketch the character on the screen and then the learner mimic it on the page, or on the screen with a pencil. The student will replicate the attempt repeatedly and without infringing others' time, without fear of guilt of late of wrong [6].

3. **Listening Skill** Listening is a cycle of knowledge and commitment to oneself. The linguistic and artistic taste needs a sound, which speaks correctly according to the sound output and the correct tone. The right tone carries the meaning and the sound, which gives its name 's language. Actually; there are several ways the machine should improve hearing skills:
 - Understand sounds: discriminating between voices and exits characters is a requirement for good speech practice, efficient listening comprehension. There are activities that require the student to listen to words and then encourage him to recognize the word he thinks he has learned by questions with multiple choices. Using machines in hearing capacity helps learners to rehearse several times. And give feedback by their marks and the mistakes they made [5].
 - Pronunciation and toning: Language laboratory computer programs help learners to understand sounds and then practice pronunciation and toning by listening and repeat activities using digital speech technology. The word is heard through the microphone and converts the sound into a digital format, which is placed on a disk. The learner is allowed to say a word through the microphone in the toning training process, and the program draws a diagram from it and compares it to a recorded graph for that phrase, and the learner sees the difference between the planners [2].
4. **Speaking Skill** The learner will have the opportunity to listen to many people's various dialogs on multiple topics and learn how to ask others' questions in certain situations, and how to answer them. The Internet also offers voice and image sites for learning to speak with students from different countries and discuss various topics[8].

This paper sought to describe the benefits of using computers in English language instruction. Consciousness of the advantages of computer technology in educating instruction has some inferences for teachers and learners alike. Teachers should be properly educated in the proper use of computers to teach language competencies. Teachers should get computer training phases to successfully teach English Language. Teachers should participate in these phases willingly as it will increase their confidence in using computers in their classrooms. To amplify the quality of their language teaching, teachers should be provided with sufficient computers, appropriate time and technical support. Teachers should know that their responsibility lies in helping their learners, simplifying their learning process, not giving the learners everything they need while using their own learning computers. Teachers should also know that teaching approach is what regulates the effect of teaching and learning English language, not computer technology. The use of computers in English classes makes the teaching environment more effective for teachers and the learning process more

gratifying for learners. To summarize; computers can only play a useful role in the language class if the teacher asks first: What do I want my students to learn today, and what is the best way for them to learn it? The answer probably won't involve the computer in most cases, but there will be occasions when the computer is the most suitable and the most enjoyable way for the students to get the job done.

REFERENCES

1. Basmah Issa Ahmad AlSaleem *European Journal of Scientific Research* · 4 March, 2020, pp.463 – 468
2. Oommen, A., Teaching English as a global language in smart classrooms with PowerPoint Presentation. *English Language Teaching*, 2012. 5(12): p. 54-61.
3. Hashemi, M., M. Azizinezhad, and M. Farokhi, Power Point as an innovative tool for teaching and learning in modern classes. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2012. 31: p. 559-563.
4. Poonpon, K., Enhancing English skills through project-based learning. *The English Teacher*, 2017: p. 10.
5. Mak, S.H.-y., Tensions between conflicting beliefs of an EFL teacher in teaching practice. *RELC Journal*, 2011. 42(1): p. 53-67.
6. Li, N., Seeking best practices and meeting the needs of the English language learners: Using second language theories and integrating technology in teaching. *Journal of international education research*, 2013. 9(3): p. 217.
7. Stille, S. and J. Cummins, Foundation for learning: Engaging plurilingual students' linguistic repertoires in the elementary classroom. *TESOL Quarterly*, 2013. 47(3): p. 630-638.
8. Uz, Ç., F. Orhan, and G. Bilgiç, Prospective teachers' opinions on the value of PowerPoint presentations in lecturing. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2010. 2(2): p. 2051-2059.